

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

**“Let’s Build our SFSC”
Event Validation Report
Responsible Partner: CREA**

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“Let’s Build our SFSC!” Event Validation Report – ITALY

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of CREA for the organisation and validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in Italy, organised on March 9th, 2023. This event is an online brokerage and networking event, to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agroBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

This document outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner. Furthermore, some suggestions are provided for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agrifood sector at local level. The reminder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the “Filiere Corta, Amicizia Lunga!” event in Italy.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

For the Italian event, CREA (Council for Research in Agriculture and the Analysis of Agricultural Economics) organized a networking event to promote the meeting between agricultural production and HORECA businesses of the metropolitan cities of Rome and Turin (Italy).

Thanks to the collaboration and availability of the Fusilli Project H2020 the agenda was shared with 60 e-mail addresses.

So, on 9 March 2023, CREA event took place, as part of the agroBRIDGES project. CREA intervened to present the project and to illustrate the opportunities and benefits that the short supply chain offers to producers and consumers. Afterwards, the producers and HORECA presented themselves. After a brief explanation of how to make one-to-one appointments, the network section consisting of four 10-minute slots was opened. The afternoon ended with some feedback and greetings.

Table 1: Event draft programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers	Location
Welcome	Greetings, presentation of the agroBRIDGES project and the Fusilli project, explanation of the use of the Brella platform	16.00 – 16.15	Borsotto Patrizia Ilenia Manetti	Brella: Central stage
Presentation: producers	Presentation of local agri-food products	16.15 – 17.15	Local food producers	Central stage
Presentation: HORECA	Presentation of local HORECA businesses	17.15 – 17.45	HORECA	Central stage
Instructions	Use of the Brella platform to fix the one-to-one meetings	17.45 – 17.55	Borsotto Patrizia	Central stage
Networking	One-to-one meetings	18.00 – 18.45	N/A	Breakout rooms
Final greetings	Comments, feed-back, wrap-up and final greetings.	18.45 – 19.00		Central stage

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For the organization and success of the event, 6 CREA researchers were involved in order to:

- define the agenda;
- develop promo material, involve by e-mail participants and publish the event on social media;
- set up the Brella matchmaking platform;
- moderate the events.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Researcher	2	Development of promo material; involvement by e-mail; publication of the event on social media	In-house	0.50 person days
Researcher	3	Definition of agenda	In-house	0.50 person days
Researcher	3	Brella platform configuration	In-house	3 person for 1 days
Session moderator	2	Coordination of the online session	In-house	1.5 person days

2.3 Event material

An agenda and a poster were prepared for the event. In addition, communication was spread on social media. Invitees were required to fill in a registration form with their personal data and email address, and a brief explanation about what they could expect from the event.

CREA sent the agenda and poster by e-mail to invitees, providing also a summary of the project and the event.

Figure 1: Flyer and Agenda "Filiera Corta, Amicizia Lunga"

Filiera corta, amicizia lunga!
Evento di networking dedicato a produttori di filiera corta e settore HORECA delle città metropolitane di Roma e Torino

Giovedì 9.03.2023 ⌚ 16.00 - 19.00 📍 Online Piattaforma Brella

Giovedì 9 marzo 2023, dalle ore 16.00 alle ore 19.00 si terrà l'incontro di networking online "Filiera corta, amicizia lunga!" sulla piattaforma BRELLA.

L'evento è organizzato dal **CREA - Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria** nell'ambito del Progetto H2020 "agroBRIDGES", in collaborazione con il Progetto H2020 FUSILLI.

Obiettivo dell'evento è quello di mettere in contatto produttori locali e aziende del settore HORECA di due aree metropolitane italiane, Roma e Torino.

Le aziende produttrici avranno la possibilità di promuovere la loro attività, i loro prodotti e di conoscere altri produttori e imprese della loro zona per esplorare collaborazioni, sinergie e accordi commerciali basati sulle filiere corte.

Durante l'evento, le realtà invitate potranno partecipare anche a sessioni di incontri *one-to-one* per discutere diverse opportunità commerciali attraverso l'area di networking della piattaforma.

agroBRIDGES
«Costruire ponti tra produttori e consumatori»

Questo progetto ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal Programma di Ricerca e Innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione europea nell'ambito del Grant Agreement N° 101000788.

Filiera corta, amicizia lunga!
Evento di networking dedicato a produttori di filiera corta e settore HORECA delle città metropolitane di Roma e Torino

Giovedì, 09.03.2023 ⌚ 16.00 - 19.00 📍 Online - Brella

Programma dell'evento

- Benvenuto e introduzione**
Saluti, presentazione dei team e introduzione ai Progetti agroBRIDGES e FUSILLI
⌚ 16.00 - 16.30
- Parola ai produttori**
Presentazione dei produttori delle città metropolitane di Roma e Torino
⌚ 16.30 - 17.30
- Il settore HORECA si presenta**
Parola alle realtà HORECA delle città metropolitane di Roma e Torino
⌚ 17.30 - 18.15
- Networking**
Incontri One-to-one tra produttori e HORECA
⌚ 18.15 - 18.45
- Chiusura e saluti**
Chiusura dell'evento con momento dedicato a curiosità e domande, saluti finali e feedback
⌚ 18.45 - 19.00

Questo progetto ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal Programma di Ricerca e Innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione europea nell'ambito del Grant Agreement N° 101000788.

Figure 2: News on CREA web

AgroBRIDGES: Filiera corta, amicizia lunga!

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https://www.crea.gov.it/web/alimenti-e-nutrizione/eventi?idEvento=4248957&isArchivio=false&pageNum=1&mese=3&anno=2023&tipologia&keywords&goBackFlag=1&fbclid=IwAR1-5ZiVhAFhI0KxiQV_8-Z1UDWWsddEBI_OqO6F-h5KkRwVtIlMgkGC8

Figure 3: News on CREA social media (Facebook)

Figure 4: Registration Form

Filiera Corta, Amicizia Lunga!

Evento di networking e brokeraggio
dedicato a produttori di filiera corta e
settore HORECA delle città metropolitane
di Roma e Torino - 09.03.2023
Piattaforma Brella

*Campo obbligatorio

1. Nome *

2. Cognome *

3. Indirizzo mail *

4. Sei un *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Produttore agricolo
 Rappresentante settore HORECA

5. Azienda di appartenenza *

6. Città metropolitana *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Roma
 Torino

7. Cosa ti aspetti dall'evento? *

Figure 5: Producers presentation on Brella

We decided to invite producers and representatives of HORECA sector from Rome and Turin metropolitan areas in order to let participants establish new links, meeting demand and offer needs of fresh production and short chain services.

Presentations of producers and their activities were followed by presentation of HORECA sector initiatives. Then, some minutes were devoted to matchmaking choices, where participants scheduled their meetings. A final session for greetings and remarks ended the event.

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The agenda and the poster were sent by email to the MAP members and some direct contacts of CREA researchers. In addition, thanks to the collaboration with the colleagues of the H2020 Fusilli project, the invitation was shared with their contacts. Participant involvement activities started one month before the event. Some reminders were sent 15 days before the event.

A few days before the event, the confirmed participants received the information to register into the Brella platform.

On the day of the event itself, a few hours before the start, a final reminder was sent.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Changes had to be made to the programme (agenda) during the event. The Brella platform made these changes possible. In particular, the presentation slots for HORECA actors were reduced as fewer people than expected attended (some had mishaps while others were unable to access the platform). The duration of the one-to-one meetings remained the same but was brought forward. In the following table the final agenda is shown.

The event allowed for collaboration with the H2020 Fusilli project, which operates in the same areas of the Beacon Region as agroBRIDGES.

During the producers' session, participants presented their activities and production, focusing on their aims, areas of work and needs. Each presentation lasted for about 4 minutes, in order to keep the attention high and to capture the interest of the other participants.

Same was done for distributors' session, in which representatives explained their activities and interests in participating in this kind of event.

These sessions were useful for the entire panel to get into the work of participants and also to understand which the most interesting entities were to meet in the matchmaking session.

Figure 6: Pictures during the Brella meeting

3.2 Event participation

9 producers participated, together with 2 distributors. There were also 2 participants belonging to Fusilli Project and 1 researchers external to CREA.

In more detail:

- 30 participants registered to the platform, out of which 20 participated on the day of the event;
- 13 one-to-one meeting requests were submitted by participants
- 9 one-to-one meetings were booked

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	9
HORECA	2
Fusilli Project	2
Researcher (external)	1
Researchers CREA	6
Total	20

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

10 responses collected through the validation questionnaire submitted.

Question	yes	no	Not sure			
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Supply Chain before this event?	9	1	0			
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I'd prefer not to answer
How useful do you think this event was for meeting professionals and companies to collaborate with?	3	3	3	1		
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I'd prefer not to answer
How useful do you think this kind of event is in seeing short supply chains as a promising business alternative?	4	3	2	1		
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I'd prefer not to answer
How useful did you find matchmaking and booking one-on-one meetings with other people to identify/negotiate collaborations?	3	5		1		1
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I'd prefer not to answer
Was the event useful in helping you find interesting collaboration opportunities with	3	1	4	2		

Question	Monthly or more	3-4 times per year	Twice per year	1 time per year	never	Prefer not to answer
other companies to develop Short Food Chains?						
Would you like another similar event to be organized in your region/territory? With what frequency?	1	3	4	1	0	1

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The event concepts were not relevant to our organization that is a research center and not a consultant or private business, but it turned out to be very interesting for our local agri-food ecosystem. Producers and HORECA engaged by CREA, working with our organization both for this project and for other kind of activities, were interested and found it a useful way to promote new links and partnership opportunities.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

Probably we would not organize a similar event in the future in our region following the same modalities, because we think that for our organization it would be much better to involve people in an in-person event, with physical group discussions. In this way it would be easier also to involve people instead of presenting them an event in a platform that they do not usually use.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Lack of knowledge of the Brella platform certainly affected the event both at the planning stage and during the event itself (although its flexibility allowed the agenda to be adapted during the event). The request to complete the validation format sent via google format attracted fewer returns than expected.